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Strategies to Support Literacy Development for Deaf and Hard of Hearing Children

A Review of the Literature

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Summary

- There is a lack of evidence to support effective strategies with Deaf and Hard of Hearing (DHH) children owing to problems with research design (experimental and quasi experimental/small sample sizes/no replication studies) and gaps in particular areas (e.g. writing).
- There is an emerging evidence base for two strategies: Visual Phonics and Foundations for Literacy, though further research into both is needed.
- Explicit instruction across all components of literacy is likely to be beneficial.
- There is a growing consensus that DHH children follow the same overall trajectory in reading development as their hearing peers, but they may require different instructional strategies.
- Phonology (either sound OR sign based) is necessary for children to become proficient readers. However, it is not sufficient on its own.
- Though phonological awareness and decoding is sometimes noted as an inconsistent predictor of reading achievement, phonological awareness training may be beneficial, even for those with poor auditory access if it is combined with visual supports (e.g. Visual Phonics).
- Morphology is more regular than phonology and direct instruction may be beneficial.
- Visual supports may be helpful in developing various areas of literacy (e.g. natural sign languages for overall vocabulary development; Visual Phonics for phonological awareness; visual supports in writing development; fingerspelling/manually coded English/simultaneous communication for morphographic instruction).
- Assessment methods used for hearing children not always appropriate for DHH children (eg. Fluency/sign aloud not equivalent)
- In spite of its importance, reading comprehension has received less attention in the research. Only tentative evidence exists for a range of comprehension strategies including explicit instruction, story grammar instruction, modified Directed Reading Thinking Activity, activating background knowledge, and use of well written, high-interest text.
- There is very scant research on strategies for writing. From the limited research available, the most compelling evidence is in the Teaching the Process approach from an intervention designed by Wolbers called the Strategic and Interactive Writing Intervention (SIWI) as well as Focus-on-Form methods.

Recommendations

Pillar 1: Enabling parents and communities to support children's literacy and numeracy development

Pillar 2: Improving teachers' and Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE1) practitioners' professional practice

Pillar 3: Building the capacity of school leadership

Pillar 4: Improving the curriculum and the learning experience

Pillar 5: Helping students with additional learning needs to achieve their potential

Explicit instruction in the various components of reading should be provided to DHH pupils. Phonological awareness is essential, though not sufficient, for DHH pupils to learn to read (Alasim & Alqraini, 2020; Andrews & Wang, 2015) and they are likely to benefit from explicit phonological instruction, especially when supplemented by Visual Phonics. Indeed, this combination has arguably the strongest evidence base to date in the literature and is noted as a potentially-evidence based instructional strategy (Trezek & Mayer, 2019). However, given that phonological decoding and awareness has been shown to explain 11% of the variance in reading ability in DHH children compared with 35% of the variance from language skills, it is essential that teachers emphasise language skills in reading instruction. Morphographic analysis instruction may provide an alternative avenue for students in word reading (Trussell & Easterbrooks, 2017).

Vocabulary development may be supported by repeated reading with structured instruction (Crowe & Guiberson, 2019; Davenport et al., 2019; Wang & Williams, 2014). Enhanced storybook interaction and shared reading may be beneficial (Crowe & Guiberson, 2019), especially for pre-school children (Entwisle et al., 2016) and for DHH English-language learners (Cannon & Guardino, 2012). Peer language modelling may also benefit DHH pupils' language development (Crowe & Guiberson, 2019).

Tentative evidence exists for a range of reading comprehension approaches including explicit instruction, story grammar instruction, modified Directed Reading Thinking Activity, activating background knowledge, and use of well written, high-interest texts (Wang & Williams, 2014). Other strategies such as Comprehension, Check and Repair strategy has had positive findings but does not constitute an evidence-base (Crowe & Guiberson, 2019).

While many interventions have positive findings in the research, they do not reach the threshold for an evidence base. Arguably the two most promising interventions are Visual Phonics and the Foundations for Literacy programme¹ (Trezek & Mayer, 2019) for pre-schoolers (Entwisle et al., 2016), including those without functional hearing who receive support through Visual Phonics (Davenport et al., 2019).

¹ For a description of this intervention, see **Lederberg, A. R., Malone Miller, E., Easterbrooks, S., Tucci, S., Burke, V., & Connor, C. M.** (2021). *Foundations for Literacy*. Retrieved 24.9.21 from <https://clad.education.gsu.edu/foundations-literacy-home/>

Pillar 6: Improving assessment and evaluation to support better learning in literacy and numeracy

Further research is needed in the effective assessment and evaluation of DHH language (Bennett et al., 2014) and literacy (Lam et al., 2020) skills. Consideration is needed for appropriate assessment methods. Signed reading fluency should not be taken as an equivalent measure of oral reading fluency (Lam et al., 2020) and may not be an appropriate accommodation for testing. Maze tests may prove more reliable and valid for DHH learners, though this diminishes somewhat with older cohorts – further evidence is needed.

Assessments of language should take into account the whole picture of language use rather than just word-knowledge and the Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals CELF may be a helpful assessment in this regard (Bennett et al., 2014).

Introduction

It is well documented that, historically, deaf and hard of hearing (DHH) children perform below their hearing peers in literacy with the median reading age often plateauing at 9 amongst DHH school-leavers (Conrad, 1979; Holt, 1993). While advances in technology coupled with earlier identification and intervention with these children have seen some improved results (Antia et al., 2009; Archbold et al., 2008; Geers, 2003; Mayer et al., 2016), these gains have certainly not impacted all DHH children (Harris et al., 2017b; Marschark et al., 2007) and difficulties in literacy attainment remain a concern. These difficulties are complex and multifaceted with problems documented in word recognition (Kyle & Harris, 2010), comprehension (Luckner & Handley, 2008), particularly inferential comprehension (Kyle & Cain, 2015), reading fluency (Luckner & Urbach, 2012), morphological knowledge (Trussell & Easterbrooks, 2017), knowledge of genre, motivation, and other skills (Luckner & Handley, 2008). Furthermore, the gap between DHH children and their hearing peers has been shown to widen as they progress through their teenage years (Dillon et al., 2012; Geers et al., 2017; Harris & Terlektsi, 2011; Harris et al., 2017a; Mayer et al., 2016). While there is a smaller body of research available on writing and DHH children, it is evident that there are also difficulties in this domain, with written production by DHH students lacking structure, detail and maturity (Strassman & Schirmer, 2012).

Given the historic poorer performance of DHH children in literacy and the documented multifaceted and complex difficulties they face in this domain, identifying effective strategies in supporting literacy development for this cohort is imperative. The aim of this review is to examine the existing research on effective strategies in literacy instruction for DHH children. It does so by collating and examining meta-reviews from the field since 2011. The search strategy is set out in the Appendix.

The research question guiding this systematic review is set out in the box below. Sixteen articles met the inclusion criteria (meta-reviews published since 2011; relating to DHH children and literacy; including information relevant to strategies for instruction or assessment). The sixteen articles represent a total of 217 studies, although since some of those studies are also meta-reviews, the total body of research evidence represented is considerably larger.

What strategies are effective in supporting literacy development in deaf and hard of hearing (DHH) children?

Limitations of the research base

Throughout the literature identified, a single theme emerges strongly: we lack an evidence base for effective teaching strategies for DHH children. A number of different measures are used to identify if findings from research constitute an evidence base (Cannon & Guardino, 2012). While there is ample research on literacy and DHH children in the field (Crowe & Guiberson, 2019), there is a noted lack of experimental and quasi-experimental research (Alasim & Alqraini, 2020; Entwisle et al., 2016) and replication studies (Entwisle et al., 2016; Trussell & Easterbrooks, 2017; Wang & Williams, 2014) meaning that the evidence base for individual strategies is lacking (Luft, 2018; Wang & Williams, 2014). Furthermore, there are consistent problems in the quality of research design, in particular with small sample sizes (Entwisle et al., 2016), confounding variables interfering with findings (Mayberry et al., 2011), the age of participants selected alongside the literacy skills assessed (Luft, 2018), and the lack of reporting on factors that are known to impact on outcomes (Mayer & Trezek, 2018). Luft's (2018) review of correlational studies examining early phonological or orthographic skills and reading comprehension is particularly revealing. She sought to examine reasons why the research base on these skills might be inconsistent for DHH children. Based on 28 studies, she concluded that there are several "age-based and construct measurement concerns in studies of relationships between early- and later-developing reading skills" (Luft, 2018, p.159) with most of the studies testing children outside the optimal ages for the constructs being measured.

Elsewhere, Mayberry, del Giudice and Lieberman (2011) caution on the wide variation in how, for example, phonological awareness and coding skills are measured in studies with DHH children. Familiarity with rhyme may be a given for most hearing children, but cannot be assumed among DHH study participants (Mayberry et al., 2011). Furthermore, while rhyme awareness has been shown to account for only 1.4% of the variance in reading skills for hearing children, it is often used as the main measure of phonological/phonemic awareness in studies with DHH children. Concluding that there is no relationship between phonological/phonemic awareness and reading outcomes in such studies

may subsequently be flawed (Wang & Williams, 2014). The consistent problems in research design and corresponding problems with the evidence base is noted by some in the field as alarming (Cannon & Guardino, 2012). In their meta-review of the field up to 2014, Wang and Williams summarise that there is insufficient quality research in the field of deaf education to establish an evidence-base in alphabets, fluency, vocabulary, morphology or text comprehension strategies and conclude that there is “an urgent need to identify the instructional approaches and strategies that will best support d/Dhh students’ reading development” (Wang & Williams, 2014, p. 13). Overall, “it is much easier to identify implications for further research than implications for practice” (Strassman & Schirmer, 2012, p. 177) – a sentiment echoed by the author of this review.

As well as the general problems relating to quality in the research base, there is a marked lack of research relating to writing with the overwhelming majority of the published literature on literacy focusing on reading (Mayer & Trezek, 2018). Within reading, investigations on phonological decoding and reading comprehension dominate with less focus on other reading-related skills such as fluency (Wang & Williams, 2014) or morphological knowledge (Trussell & Easterbrooks, 2017). Furthermore, many studies include DHH participants from a broad range of ages, often up to adults. As such, drawing conclusions for what is relevant for preschool, primary and post-primary is challenging. For example, in Luft’s meta-analysis on reading comprehension and phonics research, she summarises the findings of 28 studies. Thirteen of those studies had participants from age groups that would typically cross school age boundaries in Ireland (e.g. 3-6 year olds representing preschool and primary ages, or 7-16 year olds representing primary and post-primary ages). A further four studies had only adult participants. As such, deriving implications for teaching strategies from evidence that has such diverse participants is problematic.

Finally, many studies exclude students with additional disabilities or IQ scores below a certain level. This is likely to exclude a considerable proportion of DHH learners. There are also inconsistencies across reviews in terms of what constitutes ‘normal’ performance. For example, standard scores above 80 count as average for Mayer and Trezek (2018) in their examination of literacy of children with cochlear implantation. In their examination on performance of children in bilingual settings, the same authors include only those children reading at grade level as being within the normal range. Arguably, different proportions of children may be captured in the average range in the former versus the latter.

Narrative Report

The role of language

Language is at the heart of DHH children's learning. It is not the inability to hear, per se, but their often delayed, and continued impoverished, access to language that may cause profound developmental difficulties for this cohort (Hall et al., 2017). As a result of the centrality of language, there is a volume of research carried out on language acquisition in DHH children, but much of this research does not relate directly to literacy. As such, reviews examining language outcomes alone are not included in this review. Where language is examined as part of a study on literacy more generally, it has been included. The focus in those studies tends to be on vocabulary acquisition. There is limited support in the research for a number of vocabulary instruction strategies including: indirect vocabulary instruction using texts that allowed DHH readers to extract the meaning of the target vocabulary words; use of natural sign languages as the language of instruction; use of Total Communication; use of computer software or a tactile device; using written words in an intensive daily programme for vocabulary teaching; and use of aural/oral habilitation in vocabulary instruction with children who have received cochlear implants (Wang & Williams, 2014). Explicit instruction (sometimes with repeated reading) has also had positive outcomes for vocabulary development in pre-schoolers (Davenport et al., 2019). However, none of the strategies listed have a satisfactory evidence base and some of the reviewed research is old, dating back to the 1960s. Elsewhere, interventions for oral language that support *parents* in improving the quality of their communication with their preschool-age DHH children, such as modified versions of the Hanen "It Takes Two To Talk" and "Making Hanen Happen" programmes, also showed some promise (Entwisle et al., 2016). Note, however, that children's oral language levels were not assessed in those studies.

Language of instruction in the school has also been examined as a potential contributor to literacy attainment, namely whether Sign Bilingual programmes have better outcomes. Mayer and Trezek (2020) reviewed three studies reflecting 127 DHH pupils aged between 8-17 and found that the majority of pupils were not reading at grade level. The various methods used to report reading attainment (e.g. reading at grade level, reading within 'average range', SAT-HI mean scores and grade equivalents) leaves it difficult to collate findings across the articles reviewed. Furthermore, the authors note many weaknesses in the research base, including but not limited to the fact that sign language (in this case American

Sign Language) skills were rarely assessed (Mayer & Trezek, 2020). Overall, the authors suggest that the evidence base for Sign Bilingual programmes is lacking.

Word identification

Establishing how DHH students achieve automatic word recognition is of “enormous educational and theoretical importance” (Mayberry et al., 2011, p. 182). There is evidence to show that DHH children can learn to read words automatically (sight reading) (Wang & Williams, 2014). Owing to the particular characteristics of deafness, it is unsurprising that there a large proportion of the research in this area relates to phonology: phonological and phonemic awareness and phonological decoding. There has been considerable debate in the field as to whether phonological awareness skills are essential for DHH children to become proficient readers leading Wang and Williams (2014) to note this as “one of the most controversial topics” in the field. Largely, those on either side of this debate can be categorised into those subscribing to the Qualitative Similarity Hypothesis (QSH) (that is, that DHH children learn to read in the same way as hearing children) and those who do not subscribe to this theory (Andrews & Wang, 2015). Establishing to what extent the QSH holds true is important since it determines whether or not strategies targeting this skill in hearing children will be appropriate for DHH children. Indeed, three studies included in this review sought to establish evidence for DHH by looking at what was being done with hearing children (Cannon & Guardino, 2012; Crowe & Guiberson, 2019; Wang & Williams, 2014)

In an investigation into the QSH, Andrews and Wang (2015) review the work of nine research studies on reading and DHH children and summarise that there is overall consensus among the studies reviewed that reading follows the same developmental trajectory for DHH and hearing children and that phonology (either sound-based or visual/sign based) is necessary for reading, but that it is not sufficient on its own, a finding supported elsewhere (Alasim & Alqraini, 2020; Mayberry et al., 2011). There is also consensus that early, consistent, high-quality language intervention (regardless of the language used) is essential for later reading achievement. However, there is some debate over how DHH children reach reading milestones, in particular: the role of sound-based versus sign-based phonological processes; whether translation and transliteration of text from sign to print constitutes reading; the types of mediation strategies that teachers should use (English only versus sign-bilingual strategies); and the role of fingerspelling in English-word learning. Furthermore, while more articles subscribe to the QSH than not, they describe qualitative differences in

teaching strategies, particularly for children using sign language. As such, it would appear that while DHH may follow the same general trajectory in reading attainment as their hearing peers, the strategies their teachers need to use may be different. While the authors point to a number of potential strategies for decoding (e.g. fingerspelling, Visual Phonics, cued speech, speechreading, using the articulatory loop) there is no indication given as to the strength of the evidence base for these.

In their investigation into whether or not DHH children need access to spoken phonology to read, Alasim and Alqraini (2020) review 7 studies and conclude that a) DHH children can learn phonological awareness skills, with two studies noting that it is necessary for reading attainment, and b) they can access spoken phonology. Several reviews found evidence that DHH children may benefit from explicit phonological instruction especially when combined with visual supports such as Visual Phonics (Alasim & Alqraini, 2020; Davenport et al., 2019; Entwisle et al., 2016; Kart, 2021). In an attempt to highlight the importance of phonology for children who might not have good access to spoken language, Alasim and Alqraini (2020) posit that phonological units may be better understood as *cognitive* units, rather than sounds. Visual phonics (sometimes called See the Sound) is a multisensory system representing the phonemes of spoken English. The system comprises 46 hand gestures made near the mouth. Unlike cued speech, this is a classroom-based teaching tool that is not intended as a communication method. Its use is intended to be transient, until children have mastered the spoken phonemes. Kart (2021) reviewed the evidence base for Visual Phonics. She identified 13 studies (11 with DHH students) in the field and concluded that Visual Phonics is a promising instructional tool for children at preschool, elementary school and high-school levels. It should be noted, however, that the author did not use any of the typical quality indicators for research in evaluating the strength of the evidence base. The studies reviewed found that a broad range of children benefitted from Visual Phonics as an intervention regardless of their level of hearing loss or functional hearing, presence of an additional disability, use of cochlear implantation or communication mode (spoken language, sign language, or total communication). A wide range of phonics-based intervention programmes was used as a means of delivering the Visual Phonics intervention including Corrective Reading-Decoding A curriculum; Foundations for Literacy; Teach Your Child to Read in 100 Easy Lessons; Fountas and Pinnell Kindergarten Phonics Curriculum; The Reading Mastery I programme; and, LACES. In spite of the positive findings, only two studies examined the impact on reading comprehension and both found mixed results. Given

the core function of reading is to comprehend, these positive findings for Visual Phonics should be read with caution.

Care should be taken not to overstate the importance of phonological skills in reading for DHH children from the research base. Consideration should be given to the statistical anomalies that may arise in correlation studies examining phonics-based (constrained) skills and reading comprehension (unconstrained) skills, leading Luft to summarise that “individual study outcomes on the contributions of phonological skills to reading comprehension of DHH children remain mixed” (Luft, 2018, p. 149). Furthermore, in their meta-analysis of 57 studies on the topic of phonological coding and awareness skills, Mayberry et al. (2011) note that the relation between these skills and reading proficiency is both moderate and highly variable, explaining only 11% of the variance in reading ability with language skills predicting a much greater proportion of the variance (35%). The authors succinctly summarise the issue when they remark that “PCA [phonological coding and awareness] skills are of little help to readers when many words are unknown to them” (Mayberry et al., 2011, p. 181).

Some research examines alternative pathways to decoding print through the use of natural sign languages and manually coded forms of English. Early meta-reviews found that there was insufficient evidence from research to determine the effectiveness of fingerspelling and natural signed languages in decoding print (Wang & Williams, 2014). In a meta-review on phonological decoding and awareness, Mayberry et al. (2011) found that studies that used pseudowords had the smallest effect sizes suggesting that alternative strategies (non-phonological) may be used to decode written words by DHH pupils. This has important implications for teachers who must ensure that reading instruction with DHH children covers language skills as well as word recognition skills (Mayberry et al., 2011).

One avenue towards word-reading is using morphological knowledge. Morphology is the knowledge underpinning morphemes – the smallest meaning-bearing units of language (e.g. the word photograph is made up of two morphemes: photo, meaning light, and graph, meaning drawing). DHH children who use spoken English acquire inflection morphology in a delayed, but similar pattern as their hearing peers (Trussell & Easterbrooks, 2017). Children with milder levels of deafness have better morphological awareness than phonological discrimination. The evidence base for morphological instruction is not very well established due to a lack of research and poor design (Trussell & Easterbrooks, 2017).

In their review on the literature in this area, Trussell and Easterbrooks (2017) examined 16 studies and identified several strategies meeting the criteria to be potentially positive. There is a stronger evidence base for explicit morphological or morphographic training and for instruction that is delivered with some form of sign-support such as fingerspelling, manually coded English or simultaneous communication. Instruction that is combined with phonological training, and instruction delivered daily have both (separately) been shown to be promising. Inflectional morphological training should follow the same developmental sequence as is established for hearing children, at least when working with DHH children using spoken English. Improving the input of grammatical morphemes through amplification and increased exposure in conversation might benefit DHH learners with moderate hearing losses. For DHH bilinguals, morphographic decoding may be a more effective decoding strategy since it is visual and since it follows more regular patterns than phonology. Consideration should be given to visual supports for morphological training through e.g. manually coded English, fingerspelling, written prompts, etc. Spelling analysis tools (e.g. multilinguistic coding system) and spelling rule instruction might help address the spelling errors common in students who lack morphological knowledge, though attention needs to be given to the exceptions to spelling rules.

Reading comprehension

The core function of reading is to extract meaning from text. In spite of this, fewer meta-reviews have been carried out on the area of comprehension compared with other elements of reading, such as phonological decoding. In their review of other systematic reviews, Wang and Williams (2014) note that there has been a range of intervention studies examining the effectiveness of strategies to teach reading comprehension such as: “[using] prior knowledge, text structure, question answering, mental imagery, mnemonics, and inference making,” although the total evidence for each strategy is insufficient to determine its effectiveness with DHH readers (2014, p. 9). They point to the 52 studies reviewed by Luckner and Handley in 2008 on reading comprehension. Again, the threshold for an evidence base is not met and at best, only tentative evidence exists for the following reading comprehension strategies: “explicit instruction, story grammar instruction, modified Directed Reading Thinking Activity, activating background knowledge, and use of well written, high-interest text” (Wang & Williams, 2014, p. 10).

Reading fluency

Some evidence supports the use of independent oral reading as a strategy to improve reading fluency (Wang & Williams, 2014). Luckner and Urbach (2012 in Wang & Williams, 2014) showed that while research on repeated readings as a strategy had positive findings, the evidence base was weak and failed to meet even the ‘possible’ evidence for effectiveness threshold on a number of metrics.

Writing

Evidence on writing is sparse (Mayer & Trezek, 2018; Strassman & Schirmer, 2012) and much of the research available is dated (Strassman & Schirmer, 2012). In their review, Strassman and Schirmer carried out an extensive review of the literature on writing and hearing children and identified four critical elements for writing instruction: teaching the process approach, instruction on characteristics of quality writing, writing for content learning, and feedback. They found the most compelling evidence in teaching the process approach to emerge from an intervention designed by Wolbers called the Strategic and Interactive Writing Intervention (SIWI). This intervention is based on the cognitive apprenticeship and collaborative writing approach where instructional discourse and teacher think-alouds make explicit to students how to create quality written compositions. The SIWI approach contains two components, one aimed at students and one at teachers. The POSTER (plan, organise, scribe, translate, edit, revise) approach is to help students remember the stages involved in quality writing while NIP-it (notice, instruct, practice) helps their teachers to remember to notice what is missing from their students’ writing, provide direct instruction on that element, and provide time for students to put this into practice. The intervention has been shown to improve many components of writing for DHH students of various ability and language backgrounds. Some evidence was also available for procedural facilitation – provision of a visual support tool to assist pupils in improving their writing (Easterbrooks and Stoner, 2006).

Under the element of instruction on characteristics of quality writing, the strongest evidence emerged for an intervention that used focus-on-form methods where students receive contextualised instruction on grammar, often using the students’ generated text. The

studies by Berent et al. (2007, 2009) included DHH college students undertaking a remedial English class. Instruction focused on nine grammatical forms and those in the intervention groups of the study were provided with: passages that had the target grammatical forms enhanced to draw students' attention to them, versions of their own essays that indicated correct and incorrect use of the target grammatical forms, and passages containing the target grammatical forms projected during lessons. Unlike the control groups, the experimental groups had significant improvements in the target skill set and had good retention of this skill over time.

One study examining writing for content learning (science) demonstrated little evidence that the approaches helped students learn the target content, though some approaches (creative writing and double entry) elicited longer texts from students that had more sophisticated language constructs. Studies on the use of feedback were poorly designed leaving it impossible to ascertain the effectiveness of the interventions. Overall, the evidence base on what works for teaching DHH students how to write is dated and methodologically weak; further research is needed.

Working with particular populations

Crowe and Guiberson (2019) sought to establish an evidence-base for teaching literacy to Deaf Multilingual Learners (DMLs). In their review, they also examined the evidence base for DHH learners and hearing bilingual learners. There was no study on DMLs that met the inclusion criteria for their review and only two studies on this cohort identified in the overall search (of 144 studies). Ultimately, 7 studies on DHH learners and 10 studies on hearing bilingual learners were used to identify strategies that *might* inform practice. Only the studies on DHH learners are reported here.

The seven studies (appearing across six articles) examined a range of interventions: enhanced storybook interaction; peer language modelling; repeated reading and structured instruction; Foundations for Literacy and Visual Phonics; comprehension, check and repair strategy, and morphographic analysis instruction. The largest participant group from any study was n=5. All the interventions trialled had positive effects with only one participant out the sum total of 21 participants across the seven studies not showing some gain following the intervention. However, using the Council for Exceptional Children quality indicators, none of the studies had sufficient evidence to inform evidence based practice. Overall, while

interventions may have positive outcomes for the small numbers of participants in these studies, there is insufficient evidence to suggest they will be effective, especially with DMLs who were not part of their original research design.

Tailored approaches for DHH children

Early literacy skills can be supported with intervention programmes delivered through preschool settings such as the US-based Foundations in Literacy programme. The *Foundations in Literacy* programme is designed specifically for preschool DHH children with functional hearing, although DHH children without functional hearing can make gains if they are provided with supports such as Visual Phonics (Davenport et al., 2019) including those with cochlear implants (Entwisle et al., 2016). The evidence base for this approach is growing at Trezek and Mayer (2019) note that it meets the threshold for ‘potentially evidence-based’.

Strategies for assessment

Ongoing monitoring of progress is essential if teachers are to accurately identify gaps in their pupils’ skill set and plan their teaching accordingly. As a result, effective assessment in literacy is paramount. Bennett Gardner and Rizzi (2014) reviewed the literature to establish what tests are being used to assess ‘through-the-air’ English i.e. manually coded forms of English and found 8 assessments used 45 times over 28 articles. Lack of explicit information on how assessments should be adapted for DHH students was a theme across all the identified articles. The Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test was the most commonly used assessment in research with DHH students, being used in 17 studies out of the 28 reviewed. Since this only measures English word meaning, it is important to consider other assessments that offer a more holistic view of language. The authors point to the Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals (CELF) as the most commonly used test in research with hearing students and in *practice* with DHH students, yet it is the 6th most commonly used test in research with DHH students. They argue that it might be further considered by practitioners and researchers alike owing to its capacity to provide a comprehensive language assessment of English skills among this population. They offer some guidance on administering tests normed with hearing children to maintain validity: detailed notes should be taken and where

possible, video footage, to allow for accuracy in scoring. Some particular threats to validity can be present when tests are being administered through sign languages. In particular, iconicity of signs can make some items easier for DHH signers than for hearing children. Conversely, having multiple signs for one English word can make some items more difficult. The authors urge caution when using tests such as the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test for these reasons (Bennett et al., 2014).

Lam, McMaster and Rose (2020) also examined the issue of assessment, reporting on nine studies using curriculum-based measurement tasks specifically signed reading fluency, silent reading fluency, cloze tests and maze tests. They note that there are some challenges present in the use of signed reading fluency, in particular that different types of signing (signed English vs natural sign languages) yield different responses. Student performance on reading a signed passage 'aloud' should not be interpreted to have the same meaning as oral reading fluency. As such, they warn against using signed reading fluency as an accommodation in testing. Further research is needed to establish the use of silent reading fluency and cloze tests with DHH pupils. Maze tests had better results and may prove more reliable and valid for DHH learners, though this diminishes somewhat with older cohorts – overall, further evidence is needed in this area.

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Biography

Dr Elizabeth Mathews is an Associate Professor with the School of Inclusive and Special Education at Dublin City University, Ireland. She holds a MA in Deaf Education from Gallaudet University and a PhD from Maynooth University, Ireland. Her work in deaf education spans research, policy change and practice. She is the project lead for the Irish Sign Language STEM Glossary Project, funded by Science Foundation Ireland. Her research interests are varied and include literacy, social-emotional development, and ideology in deaf education. She is the author of *Language, Power, and Resistance: Mainstreaming Deaf Education* published by Gallaudet University Press. In 2019, after ten years of campaigning, she developed an initiative that led to policy change in Ireland allowing Deaf people, for the first time in the history of the State, to become primary school teachers.

Appendix

Research questions

What strategies are effective in supporting literacy development in deaf and hard of hearing (DHH) children?

Search terms

A search was carried out in two databases: EBSCO and SCOPUS. All 25 databases within EBSCO were included in the search. The search terms included:

“systematic review” OR “meta-analysis” OR “research synthesis”
AND
"deaf" OR "hearing impair*"
AND
“literacy” OR “reading” OR "writing".

In EBSCO, the second and third search items above were set to appear in the abstract. In SCOPUS, all three were set to title/keynote/abstract.

The term “hearing loss” was not used in the search as this is more widely used in the field of medicine, but is not common to deaf education. The search was limited to articles published from 2011 onwards and the initial search returned 73 results. Limiting results to articles or reviews in peer-reviewed publications reduced this to 62 results. Duplicates were then eliminated resulting in 45 results for screening. (excluding on health literacy for example).

The titles were then checked to ensure that the result was relevant to deafness and literacy, reducing the number of articles to 23. At that point, the abstracts were read closely and the results were further refined by eliminating two studies that did not relate to literacy and two not written in English. The remaining 19 articles were read in full. Three were eliminated: two because they were related to literacy outcomes generally but not strategies, and one because there was not sufficient information on literacy. One study (Luft, 2018), although it did not explicitly look at strategies, has been included here since it has considerable implications for the evidence base on reading and DHH children. Sixteen studies were included in the final review and are tabulated below.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Review	Number of studies	Effect size (If available)	SEN/ Disability	Age range	Findings
Alasim and Alqraini, 2020 on the need for phonological awareness to learn how to read	7	n/a	DHH	3-18	Explicit instruction with visual tools means that DHH children can acquire phonological awareness, though different approaches may be needed for different groups of DHH children depending on their functional hearing. Phonological awareness may be important for DHH children to learn to read, including those who do not have access to auditory information. Phonological awareness may be better understood as cognitive units rather than sounds in the case of DHH children without auditory access.
Andrews and Wang, 2015 on the qualitative similarity hypothesis	9	n/a	DHH	Not provided	There is overall consensus among the studies reviewed that reading follows the same developmental trajectory for DHH and hearing children. All articles reviewed support that phonology (either sound-based or visual/sign based) is necessary for reading, but that it is not sufficient on its own. There is also consensus that early, consistent, high-quality language intervention (regardless of the language used) is essential for later reading achievement. However, there is some debate over how DHH children reach reading milestones, in particular: the role of sound-based versus sign-based phonological processes; whether translation and transliteration of text from sign to print constitutes reading; the types of mediation strategies that teachers should use (English only versus sign-bilingual strategies); and the role of fingerspelling in English-word learning. Furthermore, while more articles subscribe to the qualitative similarity hypothesis than not, they

					describe qualitative differences in teaching strategies, particularly for children using sign language.
Bennett, Gardner and Rizzi, 2014 on through-the-air English skills	28	n/a	DHH		The authors reviewed the literature to establish what tests are being used to assess ‘through-the-air’ English i.e. manually coded forms of English and found 8 assessments used 45 times over 28 articles. Lack of explicit information on how assessments should be adapted for DHH students was a theme across all research articles. The Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test was the most commonly used assessment across the research identified. Only 6 out of the 28 articles used a language sample in the study.
Cannon and Guardino, 2012 on Deaf English-language learners (ELL)	5 (4 articles on ELL students with disabilities and 1 on DHH students)	n/a	DHH (some with additional disabilities)	School-aged	The authors reviewed the literature to establish best practices used with ELL students with disabilities and ELL students who were DHH. Only the literature pertaining directly to students who are DHH is included here. One study met the inclusion criteria and it implemented a shared reading intervention with DHH children who had immigrated to America. Results showed some promise for pre-teaching of vocabulary and explicit instruction. Overall, there is a complete lack of evidence base for effective instructional strategies with this population.
Crowe and Guiberson, 2019, on Deaf and/or multilingual learners	17 (7 on DHH learners and 10 on hearing bilingual learners)		DHH	Birth-21 years (though the studies on DHH students are from 3-10 years of age)	The authors sought evidence-based interventions for Deaf Multilingual Learners (DMLs), DHH learners and hearing bilingual learners. There was no study on DMLs that met the inclusion criteria and only two studies on this cohort identified in the overall search (of 144 studies). Ultimately, 7 studies on DHH learners and 10 studies on hearing bilingual learners were used to identify strategies that might inform practice. Only the studies on DHH learners are reported here.

					<p>The seven studies (appearing across six articles) examined a range of interventions: enhanced storybook interaction; peer language modelling; repeated reading and structured instruction; foundations for literacy and Visual Phonics; comprehension, check and repair strategy, and morphographic analysis instruction. The largest participant group from any study was n=5. Using the Council for Exceptional Children quality indicators, none of the studies had sufficient evidence to inform evidence based practice. Nonetheless, all the other interventions had positive effects, though they did not meet the quality indicator to inform evidence based practice. Only six studies were classified as having potential to inform evidence based practice and all were from studies on hearing bilingual learners.</p>
<p>Davenport, Watson and Cannon, 2019 on Single-Case Design Research in Early Literacy skills</p>	14	n/a	DHH	<p>Preschool 2years 0months – 7years 10 months</p>	<p>The authors examined single case design studies of interventions in preschool settings. The fourteen studies included in the review examined a range of literacy skills including alphabet knowledge, expressive and receptive language, and phonological awareness. A broad range of interventions was apparent across the studies reviewed including Foundations for Literacy (n=5), explicit instruction with repeated reading (n=2), the Endless Alphabet app (n=1), explicit instruction for vocabulary development (n=3), Shared or Interactive storybook reading (n=2), and a phonological awareness intervention (n=1). Using the What Works Clearinghouse Standards, the review notes eight studies pointing to strong evidence (though it does not specify which of the studies these are), where the number of effects was equal to the number of opportunities for an effect to occur). None</p>

					of the studies in the review met the criteria for an evidence base. Since <i>Foundations for Literacy</i> was used most often across the studies, there is a growing body of support for this curriculum for preschool DHH children, including those without functional hearing who receive support through Visual Phonics. The studies with the best quality indicators for evidence (meets standards without reservations) were those using explicit instruction (with and without repeated reading). Overall, further research is needed to build the evidence base.
Entwisle, Brouwer, Hanson and Messersmith, 2016 on emergent literacy interventions for pre-schoolers with cochlear implants	5	n/a	DHH	Preschool 3-6*years *one of the studies included in the review had participants up to 7 years.	<p>The studies reviewed found evidence for explicit phonological awareness instruction (e.g. Visual Phonics, a modified <i>Foundations for Literacy</i> curriculum, or the Fountas and Pinnel kindergarten phonics curriculum). There is also support for mother-child storytelling and shared book reading, in particular where the caregiver uses an interactive approach to the activity. Interventions for oral language such as modified versions of the Hanen “It Takes Two To Talk” and “Making Hanen Happen” programmes also showed some promise in that they improve <i>parents’</i> abilities in effective communication with their DHH children. Note, however, that children’s oral language levels were not assessed.</p> <p>The review points to limited research in this field and that what exists is not of high research design quality. The authors used the Schlosser and Raghavendra (2004) evidence appraisal hierarchy for participants with disabilities and found that the five studies included in the review scored 4 on a 5-point rating scale where 5 is the weakest study design.</p>

Kart, 2021 on Visual Phonics	13 (11 with DHH students)	n/a	DHH	Pre-K to 12 th grade	Kart found evidence supporting Visual Phonics as an instructional tool for children at preschool, elementary school and high-school levels. The studies reviewed found that a broad range of children benefitted from Visual Phonics as an intervention regardless of their level of hearing loss or functional hearing, presence of an additional disability, use of cochlear implantation or communication mode (spoken language, sign language, or total communication). A wide range of phonics-based intervention programmes was used as a means of delivering the Visual Phonics intervention.
Lam, McMaster and Rose, 2020 on Curriculum Based Measurements	9	n/a	DHH	Not given	<p>There are some challenges present in the use of signed reading fluency as a measure of curriculum based measurement (CBM), in particular that different types of signing (SEE vs ASL) yield different responses. Student performance on reading a signed passage ‘aloud’ should not be interpreted to have the same meaning as oral reading fluency; caveats on using signed reading fluency as an accommodation in testing.</p> <p>Further research is needed to establish the use of silent reading fluency, cloze tests as CBMs with this cohort. Maze tests had better results and may prove more reliable and valid for DHH learners, though this diminishes somewhat with older cohorts – further evidence is needed.</p>
Luft, 2018 on Reading Comprehension and Phonics Correlational studies	28	n/a	DHH	3years - adulthood	While school-entry phonemic awareness and letter knowledge are highly predictive of later reading success for hearing children, the research base for DHH children is not as consistent. This is possibly because of problems in how research is carried out with several “age-based and construct measurement concerns” emerging in the literature.

Mayberry, Giudice and Lieberman, 2010 on phonological coding and awareness	57	Mean z score = 0.35 $r^2 = .109$		4-62	While there is evidence of phonological coding and awareness in deaf readers, approximately half of all studies reviewed did not find a statistically significant effect for its use, suggesting it is “not a robust phenomenon” in this population. Phonological coding and awareness skill predicted 11% of the variance in reading scores. When it is included as a variable in the study, language skills predicts much more of the variance in reading proficiency (35% of the variance across 7 studies). The authors found a large and nonnormally distributed range in effect sizes leading them to conclude that “the relationship between phonological coding and awareness and reading is inconsistent across studies” (p.174). Furthermore, there is evidence that alternative strategies They conclude that the relationship of phonological decoding and awareness to reading among DHH children is of “moderate size and highly variable depending on the task” (p,182).
Mayer and Trezek, 2020 on literacy outcomes in bilingual education settings	3	n/a	DHH	Middleschool High school Gr2-9 Age 8-17	Using reading at grade level equivalent as their measure, the authors find that the majority of students enrolled in sign bilingual environments are not achieving higher levels of literacy. Problems with study design are evident and the authors caution that an evidence base is needed for sign bilingual programmes.
Strassman and Schirmer, 2012 on evidence based practice for writing	16	n/a	DHH	Preschool through to college.	The authors identified four critical elements for writing instruction from a review of literature with hearing students and used these to examine the evidence base for DHH students. Some evidence was found for particular teaching the process approaches (SIWI approach) and for instruction on characteristics of quality writing (focus-on-form methods). One study examining writing for content learning (science) demonstrated little evidence that the approaches helped students learn the target content, though some approaches (creative writing and

					double entry) elicited longer texts from students that had more sophisticated language constructs. Studies on the use of feedback were poorly designed leaving it impossible to ascertain the effectiveness of the interventions. Overall, the evidence base on what works for teaching DHH students how to write is dated and methodologically weak; further research is needed.
Trezek and Mayer, 2019 on Reading and Deafness	3	n/a	DHH	n/a	Though not a systematic review, the authors review 3 meta-reviews on literacy and deafness to examine the Simple View of Reading (SVR), specifically the role of phonological decoding in the reading process for DHH children. They conclude that, though the evidence base is lacking, “there is no compelling empirical evidence to suggest that deaf learners can become proficient readers without [phonological skills]” (p.9). Furthermore, they note that Visual Phonics and the Foundations for Literacy programme meet the threshold for potentially evidence-based practice using the Council for Exceptional Children standards.
Trussell and Easterbrooks, 2017 on morphological knowledge	13	n/a	DHH	3-21 years	The evidence base for morphological instruction is not very well established due to a lack of research and poor design. Nonetheless, several strategies meet the criteria to be potentially positive. There is a stronger evidence base for explicit morphological or morphographic training and for instruction that is delivered with some form of sign-support such as fingerspelling, manually coded English or simultaneous communication. Morphology follows more regular patterns than phonology. Instruction that is combined with phonological training, and instruction delivered daily have both (separately) been shown to be promising. Inflectional morphological training should follow the same developmental sequence as is established for hearing children, at least when working with Deaf children using spoken English. Improving the input of grammatical

					<p>morphemes through amplification and increased exposure in conversation might benefit Deaf learners with moderate hearing losses. For Deaf bilinguals, morphographic decoding may be a more effective decoding strategy since it is visual. Consideration should be given to visual supports for morphological training through e.g. manually coded English, fingerspelling, written prompts, etc. Spelling analysis tools (e.g. multilinguistic coding system) and spelling rule instruction might help address the spelling errors common in students who lack morphological knowledge, though attention needs to be given to the exceptions to spelling rules.</p>
<p>Wang and Williams, 2014 on meta-analyses on reading</p>	<p>50 studies included in the review, but only 6 of these relate to DHH learners</p>	<p>n/a</p>	<p>Three groups: -hearing -special education hearing students (including ELL) -DHH</p>	<p>Pk-12</p>	<p>The authors carried out a review of meta-analyses published on reading research since 2000. Their review included studies on hearing children which do not form part of this systematic review. Furthermore, some of the meta-reviews included in their review are already counted in this review – those findings are not repeated here. Some of the studies reflected in their findings are very old, dating back to the 1960s. Nonetheless, the article summarises the state of the research up to 2014. They summarise that there is insufficient quality research in the field of deaf education to establish an evidence-base in alphabets, fluency, vocabulary, morphology or text comprehension strategies and conclude that there is “an urgent need to identify the instructional approaches and strategies that will best support d/Dhh students’ reading development” (p.13). Tentative evidence is available for a range of reading comprehension strategies as well as the use of computer programmes to teach vocabulary.</p> <p>The authors use the Qualitative Similarity Hypothesis to support their application of research findings on effective strategies with children who are hearing to the population of DHH children. Those</p>

					findings are not reported here since strategies effective with hearing children is covered elsewhere in this review.
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